

EVALUATION OF THE INFLUENCE OF THE SUBSTITUTION OF BEAN RESIDUES IN PLASTER MATRICES

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this study was to evaluate the physical properties of plaster composites containing different quantities of bean residues: 0.00 %, 2.50 %, 5.00 %, 7.50 % and 10.00 %. These composites were molded using a water/cement ratio (w/c) of 0.6 and cured. In order to evaluate the influence of the addition of the bean residues into the plaster matrix tests of humidity, apparent density, water absorption, thermal conductivity and acoustic insulation were carried out. In general, satisfactory results were obtained; there was a decrease in apparent density, improvement in sound insulation and stability of thermal conductivity.

KEYWORDS

Natural fibers; residues; low environmental impact products.

INTRODUCTION

Cement is the second most consumed material in the world, after water. It has been used by man in the construction of their homes and due to the incessant search to adapt it to the new needs of civil construction, it has seen remarkable evolution. In fact, cement has several qualities, however, in order to make its production possible, the environment suffers severe damage, such as the degradation and contamination of water and soil and the release of atmospheric gases that increase the greenhouse effect and can cause respiratory problems to the local population (Maury and Blumenschein, 2012).

In order to reduce the production and consumption of cement, different forms of substitution for other materials have been studied. According to Vimmrová *et al.* (2011), gypsum plaster is a great alternative to cement, since it is already widely used in internal finishing in civil construction and which, when compared to conventional binders, has the advantages of the easy preparation method, high cost benefit, great ability to mold itself into different shapes, good thermal insulation and ability to regulate humidity inside homes. In addition, it has a compressive strength level within the recommended standards.

On the other hand, plaster has low tensile and flexural strength (Kuqo and Mai, 2021). These disadvantages may be limiting factors in the use of plaster, since in some of its applications superior mechanical and physical properties to those presented by the material are required. According to Bijen and van der Plas (1992), the incorporation of fibers as reinforcement in plaster is recommended for greater efficiency of the material in structures.

Fiber-reinforced materials have mostly improved energy dissipation, stiffness, ductility, and impact resistance. With this in mind, a wide variety of reinforcements have been used, such as the following synthetic and natural fibers: glass fibers (Martias *et al.*, 2014), textile fibers, polyamide fibers, polypropylene fibers (Medina and Barbero-Barrera, 2017; Gencel *et al.*, 2014), microfibers from shredded tires (Parres *et al.*, 2009), among others. However, synthetic fibers are increasingly losing

ground to natural fibers due to their non-renewable and non-biodegradable nature (Li and Li, 2014; Lushnikova and Dvorkin, 2015).

Natural fibers present, in this context, renewable nature, biodegradability, low density, low cost, good combination of mechanical and physical-thermal properties and good interaction with matrix phases. In addition, natural fibers have the potential to increase the performance and mechanical, physical, thermal and acoustic characteristics of the composites that contain them. In the literature, research has already been done about the interaction of natural fibers with plaster matrices and their proportions in relation to physical characteristics (Di Bella *et al.*, 2014; Pierre *et al.*, 2010). Different natural fibers have been used for that, such as sisal, cotton stalk, wood, date palm (Djoudi *et al.*, 2014), palm kernel fruit, kenaf, coconut (Tilak *et al.*, 2015), among others.

Another type of natural fiber, still not often used in civil construction, are the fibers from bean residue. With a great abundance and potential to add to the physical characteristics of plaster, they present themselves as a possible improvement for this product. According to CONAB (2020), the planting of beans in Brazil is carried out on a large scale, with the harvest in 2020/2021, for example, reaching the production of approximately 266 million tons of beans. It is estimated that the production of residues, pods, branches, stems, leaves, roots, etc. from this crop is about 146 million tons. Part of this waste is underused or even disposed of incorrectly in nature.

The objective of this study is, in this context, to evaluate the interactions between bean fibers and plaster matrices and to compare the physical properties of plaster with the incorporation of different fiber content of bean residues (0.00 %, 2.50 %, 5.00 %, 7.50 % and 10.00 %), aiming to analyze the feasibility of this low environmental impact composite.

METHODOLOGY

To carry out the research, bean fiber residue (*Phaseolus vulgaris*) (stem and pod) was collected from the Pimentas farm, located in the municipality of Lavras (latitude 21°15'58.5" S and longitude 45°03' 31.5" W). The plaster used in the molding was purchased locally in Lavras, Minas Gerais, Brazil, with specifications in accordance with EN 14496 (CEN, 2017).

The bean residue was sent to the Experimental Unit for Wood Panels (UEPAM) at the Federal University of Lavras (UFLA), processed in a high-speed hammer mill and sieved. The selected particles were those passing through the 20 mesh sieve and retained on the 40 mesh sieve.

After preparing the raw materials, the composites were molded from the raw materials described above through 5 treatments described below (Oliveira *et al.*, 2020):

- T1 - 100.00 % plaster and 0.00 % bean residue;
- T2 - 97.50 % plaster and 2.50 % bean residues;
- T3 - 95.00 % plaster and 5.00 % bean residue;
- T4 - 92.50 % plaster and 7.50 % bean residues;
- T5 - 90.00 % plaster and 10.00 % bean residue.

The dimensions of the specimens were 40.00x40.00x160.00 mm, according to the EN 13279-2 (CEN, 2014). Six specimens were molded per treatment, with a water/plaster ratio of 0.6, as recommended by (Oliveira *et al.*, 2020). During the period of 24 hours, the specimens solidified, allowing their demolding and storage in a well-ventilated place, free from the action of weather. Tests were performed after the seventh day of curing.

After making the specimens, the tests shown in Table 1 were carried out in order to evaluate the influence of the bean residue on the properties of the composites.

Table 1: Tests used in this research.

Test	Standard
Moisture on dry basis	NBR 7190 (ABNT, 1997)
Apparent density	NBR NM 45 (ABNT, 2006)
Water Absorption	ASTM D570-98 (ASTM, 2018)
Thermal conductivity	JIS 1412-2 (JSA, 2016)
Sound insulation	ISO 10534-2 (ISO,1998)

In order to verify the effects of treatments on the quality of the panels, a completely randomized design was used. The data from the analyzed properties were submitted to linear regression, analysis of variance (ANOVA) and also to the Tukey test at 5.00 % probability, to compare the means.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Moisture

Moisture of composites from different treatments is shown in Figure 1.

*Means followed by the same letter in the line do not differ at 5.00 % probability by the Tukey test.

Figure 1: Moisture content results

An initial decrease in moisture is observed when incorporating bean fiber residues up to 5.00 %. Beyond this level of replacement, the moisture increases with the amount of waste incorporation. According to Veloso *et al.* (2021), the increase in hydrophobicity with the insertion of the residue is a beneficial characteristic for plaster, since it can reduce its restriction to dry environments and expand its use for composites. According to the authors, the increase in moisture occurs due to the combination of cellulose and hemicellulose (holocellulose), which, due to its hygroscopic character, causes the product to adsorb more moisture. The decrease in moisture occurs due to the lignin and extractive contents of the residue.

Humidity also presented great variations among the different treatments, finding statistically equivalent results only for 0.00 % and 7.50 %. A decrease of 66.60 % was found between the moisture of the specimen of 0.00 % and 5.00 % and an increase of 246.00 % between 0.00 % and 10.00 %. According

to Chinta *et al.* (2013) a controlled increase presents values below 200.00 % and, therefore, the increase in humidity in the treatment of 10.00 % incorporation is considered uncontrolled, while the other results can be considered as controlled.

The maximum variations found are between 66.60 % and 246.00 %. In those composites containing 2.50 % and 5.00 % bean residues, where humidity decreased, values found were close to those found by Veloso *et al.* (2021), who studied plaster composites reinforced with particles of cocoa agro-industry residue. On the other hand, in composites containing 7.50 % and 10.00 % bean residue, in which an increase in humidity was observed, the results are close to those found by Chinta *et al.* (2013), who studied plaster composites reinforced with plant fibers and de Oliveira *et al.* (2020) who studied composites with plaster matrix reinforced with wood fibers.

Apparently density

The results of the plaster composites density test are shown in Figure 2.

*Means followed by the same letter in the line do not differ at 5.00 % probability by the Tukey test.

Figure 2: Apparent density of composites

The density of the material was stable across all treatments, with minimal variations. Comparing the values found, it is observed that the five treatments were statistically equal, according to Tukey's Test ($\alpha = 0.05$).

In general, the apparent density of the material decreased, ranging from 1.62 g/cm³ to 1.40 g/cm³. This occurs because the specific mass of plaster is greater than that of bean fiber residues. The decrease in composite density in comparison to the matrix is reported in other studies, such as Rivero *et al.* (2014), who incorporated rubber into the plaster matrix, Chinta *et al.* (2013), who made plaster composites reinforced with plant fibers and Morales-Conde *et al.* (2016), who incorporated demolition wood waste into plaster-based composites.

Water absorption

Figure 3 shows the water absorption graph of plaster composites at 2 (WA2h) and 24 (WA24h) hours.

* Significant regression analysis at 5 % significance.

Figure 3: Water absorption results

It is observed that when incorporating different percentages of bean fiber residue, water absorption values increased, presenting the highest value at 5.00 %, in both graphs. Veloso *et al.* (2021) found that water absorption decreased with the increase of lignocellulosic residue content, contrary to the results found in this research. This difference is due to the lignin content of the fiber, since lignocellulosic materials have hydrophobic characteristics, being responsible for the decrease in water absorption. The bean fiber had 8.13 % lignin, while cocoa has 35.15 % (Veloso *et al.*, (2021)).

It is noted that most of the water absorption in the composite specimens refers to the first two hours of curing. The specimen with 0.00 % of bean fiber residues presents 74.00 % of the absorption in the first two hours, when compared to the 24-hour graph. The specimens with the incorporation of bean fiber residues showed similar behavior, presenting an average of 98.00 % of the water absorption in the first two hours.

Thermal conductivity

Figure 4 presents the results of thermal conductivity of the plaster composites with different content of bean residues.

*Means followed by the same letter in the line do not differ at 5 % probability by the Tukey test.

Figure 4: Thermal conductivity results.

These results point to a small difference between treatments. The 0.00 %, 2.50 %, 5.00 % and 7.50 % specimens are statistically equivalent. In addition, the result of the 10.00 % sample differs from the reference but is statistically equal to the other specimens.

Thermal conductivity results range from 0.28 W/mK to 0.32 W/mK. Noronha (2014) obtained similar results in the mixture of plaster with pulp from Kraft paper, with a thermal conductivity of 0.25 W/mK and in the mixture of plaster with banana fiber, with a thermal conductivity of 0.44 W/mK. Medeiros (2017) also found similar results when incorporating different materials into a plaster matrix: leather residue, plain paper, Kraft paper and Vinyl Acetate (EVA) powder, with the respective values of 0.25 W/mK, 0.24 W/mK, 0.23 W/mK and 0.23 W/mK.

According to Villela *et al.* (2020), plaster has low thermal conductivity, due to the low conductivity of the air trapped in its pores, which causes the material to be resistant to the passage of heat.

Acoustic Insulation

Figure 5 shows the results of the sound insulation test. In relation to the control, the composites reduced the sound intensity in all analyzed frequencies. These results are in agreement with those observed by Veloso *et al.* (2021) for plaster-based composites reinforced by lignocellulosic residues. Sound absorption in plaster composites is related to their porosity, especially to the presence of interconnected pores (Jia *et al.*, 2021). When a porous material, such as plaster, is exposed to sound, the air molecules inside the pores of the material vibrate, transforming some energy into heat (Moretti *et al.*, 2016). Composites containing bean residues showed reductions in the intensity of the sound on average 0.23 dB higher compared to the reference material, across all frequencies. At the frequency of 1000.00 Hz, the greatest differences between treatments can be observed. At this frequency, the composite containing 10.00 % of bean residue presented the best result, with a measured sound intensity of 46.40 dB, while for the control the measured value was 57.27 dB.

Figure 5: Acoustic insulation of composites.

CONCLUSION

This study presented the physical characterization of plaster composites reinforced with bean particles. From the search, the following results are obtained:

- Humidity results ranged from a decrease of 66.60 % (between 0.00 % and 5.00 % specimens) to an increase of 246.00 % (between 0.00 % and 10.00 % specimens) in comparison to the reference material. There was an initial decrease in moisture when incorporating the bean fiber residues up to 5.00 % and, beyond this level of replacement, humidity increased rapidly with residue incorporation;
- In general, the apparent density of the material was stable, with statistically equal values being obtained among the different treatments. There has been, however, a small decrease, with values ranging from 1.62 g/cm³ to 1.40 g/cm³;
- Regarding water absorption, the specimens without the incorporation of bean residues absorbed 74.00 % water within the first two hours, while the specimens with the incorporation of the lignocellulosic material absorbed 98.00 % of the water within the same timeframe. There is, therefore, an increase in water absorption when incorporating this residue, with the highest value observed being with 5.00 % incorporation;
- Thermal conductivity ranged from 0.28 W/mK to 0.32 W/mK. However, results were not statistically different for most specimens, indicating that the incorporation of bean residues has little effect on this property.
- Finally, the composites showed good acoustic insulation. In relation to the control, all specimens reduced the sound intensity in all analyzed frequencies. Furthermore, composites containing bean

residues presented reductions to sound intensity on average 0.23 dB higher compared to the reference material.

Therefore, these preliminary results point to a trend towards the feasibility of utilizing this agricultural by-product in the production of plaster composites.

New research is required, however, for a better understanding of the morphological, chemical and mechanical properties of these materials. The use of pre-treatments on the bean residue particles aiming at improving the main problem found in this research, the affinity of this material with water, should also be explored.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

1. Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.